

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF PROCESSES

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Anastasia. The article highlights the importance of the introduction of methods based on an innovative approach in the teaching of " Information technologies and mathematical modeling of processes" in the period of reforms in the higher education system , as well as the results of the impact on the quality and efficiency of education.

Keywords: information technology , model , modeling , mathematical model , innovative educational technologies .

Inter:Reforms implemented in the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years, along with ensuring that students acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications from pedagogues working in the system, it is important to achieve that they can effectively use information technologies in the field of their choice. As a result, there will be an opportunity to prepare mature and qualified personnel to work in various fields in the future. In order to achieve these goals, teachers are required to be able to effectively use innovative and modern pedagogical methods in the organization of classes, and to master the effective use of various practical software tools by students.

The rapid application of information technologies in medicine and pharmaceuticals, among many fields, has a significant impact on the development of these fields. Especially, the use of information technologies for the purposes of modeling medical-biological processes is considered important and promising. The development of mathematical models and the widespread use of information technologies in this process allow saving time and resources in conducting scientific research to study life processes, diagnose diseases and create new and effective methods of treatment.

Based on this, there is growing opinion that in the process of conducting effective scientific research in the field of pharmacy, it depends on the availability of highly qualified medical personnel with appropriate knowledge and training in the use of information technologies [1]. Our republic has personnel training programs and resources, but they do not meet the requirements of the developing industry. In our country, "Mathematical

modeling of information technologies and processes" is taught as a separate subject in medical institutions of higher education to pharmacy students as a series of lectures based on presentations in small groups of students. In these classes, little attention is paid to the independent study of students, as well as to the interpretation of research conducted in the field of pharmacy [2]. At the end of the course, a final survey will be conducted in oral or written form or in the form of computer tests.

Also, one of the problems in teaching "Information technologies and mathematical modeling of processes" in the field of pharmacy is the limitation of the ability to demonstrate various experimental processes, the reason for which is that many experiments last for a long time and there are insufficient educational institutions' bases. It is for this reason that in the process of acquiring knowledge, skills and qualifications related to this subject, it is necessary to study the possibilities of using electronic educational resources, including multimedia tools, along with traditional resources [3].

Inspired by the reforms implemented in the higher education system in our country, we decided to conduct scientific research and pedagogical experiments in order to develop a new approach to teaching "Information technologies and mathematical modeling of processes" based on innovative technologies. To achieve this goal and to teach students the basics of information technology, we have developed a new curriculum that allows for the wide use of modeling programs in the field of pharmaceuticals in scientific research related to their professional activities, as well as the creation of textbooks, training manuals and multimedia textbooks. work is underway.

Special attention is paid to the development of theoretical, practical and creative thinking in students, using a combination of productive and reproductive methods in the improvement of existing teaching methods. The use of such a combination of methods takes into account teaching students the ability to see the problem situation and find the best solutions to get out of these problem situations, and also helps them to actively participate in the lesson. They no longer receive ready-made knowledge, but must look for a way to solve a new problem based on their own experience and skills. Another important aspect: the problem situation makes students realize their lack of knowledge, encourages them to search for new knowledge and skills. Research is one of the most important conditions for the development of creative thinking [4]. Also, this structure of the lesson encourages students to learn.

The combination of these methods was tested on the students of parallel

groups of the pharmaceutical department of the Asian International University. Control and experimental groups were selected during the pedagogical experiment. In the first group, the training was conducted using traditional methods, and in the second group, using the combined methods based on an innovative approach.

In teaching using an innovative approach, we have identified positive changes in the learning and mastering of resources by students, which helps to form skills for solving future professional problems based on information technology knowledge. During the survey conducted among the students after the lessons, we found out the opinions of the students about the innovative activity, and they all gave a positive assessment.

Analysis of the results of the experiments based on the Student's criterion showed the effectiveness of the innovative approach in the experimental groups compared to traditional lessons in the control groups. The high efficiency of the new methods used in the lessons was also helped by the use of electronic resources and multimedia tools, because they allowed to demonstrate the essence of the main concepts in a visual form [5,6].

Ultimately, the result of applying an innovative approach to teaching information technologies is an improvement in the quality of education, which is manifested in a certain degree of systematization and interdependence of the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students. Students' interest in science increases due to the use of multimedia textbooks, which include electronic lectures, virtual 3D images, control questions, mandatory test tasks and exercises, including reading and interpreting the results of pharmaceutical research. All of the above is an effective means of teaching students basic IT competencies and promotes self-directed student learning. In particular, the results of the survey conducted among students also testify.

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